

A Critical Examination of Pakistan-US Relations

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Abstract

Both countries worked together in a variety of areas, with the United States giving Pakistan with economic, social, and military assistance. Two of the most well-known treaties and pacts made between the two countries to develop and improve relations were CENTO and SEATO. Pakistan has always satisfied American wishes, whether it is the Afghan War or the War on Terror. Both conflicts had devastating implications for Pakistan, with the country losing both economic and human resources. As a result of drawing Pakistan into direct warfare, trust between the two countries has eroded. Pakistan is still suffering as a result of US wars and requires financial support to recover.

Introduction

Following Pakistan's independence as a sovereign state, the US formed ties with the country and welcomed them as partners. Both countries collaborated in numerous fields, with the US providing Pakistan with economic, social, and military aid. CENTO and SEATO were two of the most well-known accords and pacts formed between the two countries in order to enhance and improve relations (Mazhar & Goraya, 2010). Pakistan and India went to war in 1965, and Pakistan expected US support. Unfortunately, this did not materialize, and the US declined to supply Pakistan with military help. It was a heartbreaking moment for Pakistan when its ally failed to come up in a time of need, demonstrating to them that their alliance is untrustworthy. In 1971, India and Pakistan engaged in yet another global war; as a result, Pakistan lost its eastern part (Bangladesh), and the United States showed no remorse (Hasnat, 2011). Under the Pressler Amendment, the United States placed sanctions on Pakistan in 1990, halting all military aid. In front of Pakistan, the United States has lost all credibility. Pakistan retaliated against India's nuclear development with a nuclear test in 1998, making it the first Muslim country to do so (Hameed, 2012). Though, this was a frightening situation in Washington, and President Clinton postponed the visit to Pakistan. Under the Glenn Amendment, the US government imposed fresh sanctions on Pakistan, restricting the supply of military gear and other loans. Following 9/11, the United States expressed interest in reestablishing ties with Pakistan and supporting them in the War on Terror. Despite previous interactions with the US, Pakistan totally cooperated with them (Yusuf, 2012).

Liaquat Ali Khan visited the United States:

In the 1950s, Pakistan's first Prime Minister, Liaquat Ali Khan, visited the United States, where both state representatives shared their beliefs of working for a better future. Pakistan was in desperate need of infrastructure and growth, and the United States offered to assist them in any way possible. As a result, it is apparent that the United States severely required Pakistan's help because India had joined the Communist alliance with the Soviet Union. As a result, the United States took advantage of Pakistan's assistance in gaining access into the South Asian region (Z. ul A. Malik, Fatima, & Zhilong, 2018).

Pakistan acted as a bridge between China and the United States:

Nonetheless, Pakistan acted as a bridge between China and the United States, sending Secretary of State Henry Kissinger to Beijing. Pakistan has traditionally held both states in high respect and wished to maintain the status quo. In contrast to the United States, China has always shown a strong interest in Pakistan, supporting them economically and militarily (Nizamani, 2018).

The United States considers China's expanding economy to be a threat signal:

The United States considers China's expanding economy to be a threat signal. Pakistan has always done its utmost to deal with misunderstandings between the two countries. Pakistan and China are engaged on a number of initiatives that the US finds undesirable. Pakistan, on the other hand, welcomed the US in exchange for a

calm atmosphere. The United States, on the other hand, has shown a greater interest in India than in China, which is causing instability in the South Asian region (Rivalry & Asia, 2015).

The 1965 war between Pakistan and India:

The 1965 war between Pakistan and India was an unexpected incident in which Pakistan had hoped for military support from the United States, but this did not materialise (Gill, 2019). Despite the fact that the pacts signed between the two countries were legitimate proof that the US would assist Pakistan in the aftermath of the war (Swami, 2007).

Establishing a new sort of balance of power:

Nixon's proposal for establishing a new sort of balance of power, which aspired to incorporate new nations, was announced (Sial, 2014). Pakistan endorsed the plan, which stressed enlisting China as an ally. As a result, Beijing was cut off from the rest of the world. Both countries did not gain from the policy in the long run (Panda, 2012). On the other hand, Bangladesh was established, leaving Pakistan with only one armed force.

India conducted the world's first nuclear test:

In 1974, India conducted the world's first nuclear test, dubbed "Smiling Buddha" (Dhanda, 2010). From India's standpoint, it was a benign test, but it was actually designed to counter China's nuclear deterrence. According to sources, the incident was caused by NATO troops, however following an inquiry, it was determined that it was not an accident. Another incident occurred the same year, when a clandestine US military contractor called Raymond Davis opened fire in a public area in Lahore, killing two Pakistani civilians. Anti-American attitudes in Pakistan grew as a result of the public outrage. NATO struck two Pakistani checkpoints in the Pak-Afghan border region in 2011, killing 24 Pakistani soldiers. Insurgent forces are undermining the country across the Pak-Afghan border (Roberts, 2009). Pakistan has sent the United States a considerable amount of records relating to these operations that take place in the country. (Tariq & Marwat, 2015).

Invading Afghanistan in the late 1970:

Invading Afghanistan in the late 1970s, the Soviets grabbed control of the entire country with their red army. Once again, the US seeks Pakistan's assistance in overthrowing the communists from power in the country. With Pakistan's support, the Soviets were beaten, and the US seized the opportunity. As a result, Pakistan has been allocated \$3.2 billion in aid for the next six years (Imran & Xiaochuan, 2017).

Pakistan successfully conducted six nuclear tests in 1998:

Because of the demise of the Soviet Union, the relationship between Pakistan and the United States stabilised after the Afghan war ended. On the other hand, despite India's unlawful nuclear status, the US was encroaching on its territory, and India was displaying a hostile attitude toward Pakistan on the border. Pakistan successfully conducted six nuclear tests in 1998. This is a historic time for Pakistan, but the United States does not recognise it, and distances have resurfaced once more (Kristensen & Norris, 2015).

War on Terrorism:

Following the terrorist attacks on the Twin Towers, the United States requested its partners to assist them in the fight against terrorism in Afghanistan. Pakistan was seen as a major partner in terms of assisting them in the region. The two countries' relations were repaired, and the US requested Pakistan's direct assistance. Despite this, Pakistan's security and economy have been severely harmed by the war on terror. Nonetheless, Pakistan played a critical role in regional counter-terrorism and provided logistical and psychological support to the US, although this was not appreciated in the long run. Pakistan now finds itself in the midst of the Afghan war on its own soil (Hasan, 2005). Pakistan's economic and welfare indicators have been devastated by the war on terror, and it will take a long time to restore them. Pakistan's economy and prosperity should be supported by aid packages from the US. There are some US-funded development projects in Pakistan, such as US aid, but more is needed (Yaseen & Muzaffar, 2018).

The National Action Plan (NAP):

Pakistan has been the world's worst victim of terrorism, with many innocent lives lost as a result of the War on Terror. Pakistan's law enforcement agencies are doing an outstanding job in starting a huge counter-terrorism campaign across the country. With the support of the National Action Plan (NAP), a number of terrorist outings are prohibited within the country. Despite all the efforts made by the Pakistani side, the American motto of "Do More" remains unabated (Sahill, 2017).

Afghan Refugees:

On the guidance of the United States, Pakistan welcomed a large number of Afghan refugees after the Afghan War. The majority of the refugees were unregistered, posing a significant economic burden on the government. In the current situation, Pakistan is deporting all Afghan refugees despite providing them with assistance for nearly two decades. The US is strongly opposed to this step and wants Pakistan to detain them for a longer period of time. As a result, the government is dealing with an overpopulation problem and is unable to accommodate them owing to security and economic concerns (Borthakur, 2017).

Pakistan and India are engaged in a massive arms race:

The United States is concerned that Pakistan and India are engaged in a massive arms race, which is jeopardising the stability of the South Asian area (Iqbal, Iqbal, Uzzaman, Malik, & Munir, 2021). In this perspective, Pakistan is acting as a responsible nuclear power that adheres to international nuclear treaties. India has a long history of breaking international conventions. Despite the fact that both countries are non-signatories to the Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT), Pakistan has always upheld its commitment to prevent any proliferation-related activity (Z. U. A. Malik & Zhilong, 2019).

The Kashmir conflict between Indian and Pakistan:

The Kashmir conflict is one of the oldest at the United Nations, and Pakistan has long wanted America to understand the importance of finding a genuine solution to the matter. The United States has traditionally treated this problem lightly so as not to jeopardise its ties with India (Khan et al., 2021).

Pakistan and China are two of the most important partners in the South Asian region:

Pakistan and China are two of the most important partners in the South Asian region, and they are working on massive projects together. Because both China and Pakistan are producing massive economic and defence equipment on an indigenous basis, the US does not appear to tolerate their long-standing friendship. The China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), which is anticipated to cost around 62 billion dollars, is one of the flagship projects led by the states. Energy projects, trade, rail, motorways, dams, and a harbour are all part of the joint venture. Pakistan uses highways to do business and uses Gwadar Port to transfer commodities. As a result, the United States' stance toward this initiative is unsatisfactory, and propaganda is being spread that China's engagement in Pakistan is increasingly akin to colonisation. As a result, as a superpower, the United States should value this endeavour and extend an invitation to join this venture, which can benefit all states (Rafay, Malik, Zhilong, & Fatima, 2020).

Conclusion

In international politics, Pakistan has always satisfied American wishes, whether it is the Afghan War or the War on Terror. Both conflicts had devastating implications for Pakistan, with the country losing both economic and human resources. As a result of drawing Pakistan into direct warfare, trust between the two countries has eroded. Pakistan is still suffering as a result of US wars and requires financial support to recover. Pakistan and the United States of America should sit down together to work out their differences and disagreements. Both countries can organise a joint committee where their officials can discuss their concerns, and this will serve as a link between them. However, the US-Pakistan connection must be enforced because a superpower's backing is critical in world affairs. As a result, America's assistance for Pakistan is critical to maintaining international peace and security.

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